

Antibacterial Effect of *Aloe vera* Ethanol Extract Against the Growth of Bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* through ZOI Test, MIC and MBC Measurement

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Abstract

Staphylococcus aureus is a gram-positive bacterium while *Escherichia coli* is a gram-negative bacterium that often causes infections and be used as a bacteriological model for many antibacterial screenings. Aloe vera is known to have active compounds that act as antibacterial, however, the effect of Aloe vera ethanol extract on the inhibition of growth and death of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* bacteria is not clear yet.

Aloe vera was extracted using maceration in ethanol. Phytochemical tests were carried out to determine the active compounds in the extract [3]. To measure antibacterial efficacy, a disc diffusion method using concentrations of 3,125%, 6,25%, 12,5%, 25%, 50%, 100%, control (+) and control (-) was done using *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Data analysis using One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test and then continued Tukey's Post Hock test with a significance of $p < 0.05$ [4] Minimum Inhibition Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) was then determined with the same concentrations.

The study's *Aloe vera* ethanol extract contained flavonoids and alkaloids. The zone of inhibitions diameter on both bacteria at the concentration of 3.125%, 6.25%, 12.5%, 25% and the negative control were 0 mm. At 50% concentration, the diameter was 7.67 ± 0.58 mm, while at 100% concentration was 20.67 ± 1.53 mm. The diameter of tetracycline and amoxicillin were 34 mm and 36 mm, respectively. MIC and MBC of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract against *Staphylococcus aureus* at a concentration of 12.5% while against *Escherichia coli* at a concentration of 25%. *Aloe vera* ethanol extract has antibacterial effects and is able to inhibit and kill *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* bacteria with higher inhibitory power against *Staphylococcus aureus* than against *Escherichia coli*.

Keywords: Extract, Ethanol, *Aloe vera*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, Antibacterial

Introduction

Infectious diseases can be defined as diseases caused by pathogens or their toxic products¹. Bacterial infectious diseases classified based on the structure of their cell wall are divided into two, namely gram-negative bacteria and gram-positive bacteria. One of the most common gram-negative bacterial species causing infection is *Escherichia coli* with an estimated mortality rate of 12%², while in gram-positive bacterial infections, *Staphylococcus aureus* is the most dominant species with mortality rates ranging from 2.8-66%^{3,4}.

Treatment of bacterial infections uses antibiotics, but use with incorrect dosage or without indication is known to result in antibiotic resistance⁵. In 2019, antibiotic resistance caused the deaths of about 5 million people worldwide. *Escherichia coli* most commonly resistant to aminopenicillin (46.8%)⁶, while *Staphylococcus aureus* are resistant to some antibiotics ranging from 13-82% to high levels of resistance to penicillin (82%) and methicillin (46%)⁷.

Based on previous research, the *Aloe vera* plant or commonly known as aloe vera contains compounds such as saponins, flavonoids, phenols, alkaloids and terpenoids that are antibacterial^{8,9,10}. In research conducted by Azahra et al in 2019, *Aloe vera* aqueous extracts had an antibacterial effect and was bactericidal¹¹. In another study, ethanolic extracts resulted in higher extract yield where the higher the extract yield produced the higher the content of the active substance or compound attracted¹².

In this research, the antibacterial effect of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract are determined through measuring the diameter of the zone of inhibition, determination of the ZOI test, measurement of MIC and MBC against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Research Methods

Design, Place and Time of Research

This research is an in vitro laboratory research using a post-test control only group design. The research was conducted at the Laboratory of the Faculty of Medicine, Islamic University of Malang from November 2023 to January 2024.

Research Sampling

Samples of *Aloe vera simplisia* with Batch No. 230911.LDB. J.MMB. CO3 is obtained from the Technical Implementation Unit (UPT) of Materia Medika Batu.

Manufacture of *Aloe vera* Ethanol Extract

The extract was made by soaking 200 mg of *simplisia* with 1000 ml of 70% ethanol solvent, after which it was allowed to stand for 24 hours in a tightly closed beaker glass. The extract was then filtered with a vacuum Buchner and collected into an Erlenmeyer tube. The extract was evaporated for 2-3 hours at 50°C using a rotary evaporator, then put into an oven at 50°C for 1 day, aimed to remove 70% ethanol content from the extract¹³.

Phytochemical Testing

Phytochemical testing was performed on 5 ml of *Aloe vera* ethanolic extracts. The extract was put into a separate funnel filled with a mixture of chloroform and ethanol 70% solvent in a ratio (20 ml: 20 ml) then shakes for 20 minutes, then left it in a separating funnel until two layers consisting of chloroform and filtrate were formed, then the two phases were separated. The filtrate phase is used to test secondary metabolites of flavonoids, phenolics and saponins while the chloroform phase is used to test for alkaloids and terpenoids¹⁴.

Inhibition Zone Testing by Well Diffusion

Bacterial inhibition zone testing begins by mixing 1 ose suspension of *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria into a test tube containing 5 ml of sterile NaCl solution then homogenized using vortex and the turbidity was standardized to the 0.5 *McFarland* standard so that the number of bacteria meets the standard for sensitivity tests, namely 10⁵-10⁸ CFU / ml. A standardized bacterial solution was applied to *Muller Hinton Agar* (MHA) media then the MHA media was perforated with *Aloe vera* extract, negative control and positive control using micropipettes into each hole in MHA media then incubated it into the incubator at 37 ° C for 24 hours. The test was repeated 3 times. The same was done on *Escherichia coli* bacteria then observed and measured the diameter of the *clear zone* formed around the hole using a caliper¹⁵.

Minimum Inhibition Concentration Measurement

MIC measurement using *Aloe vera ethanol extract* concentrations of 3.125%, 6.25%, 12.5%, 25%, 50%, 100%. The first step is to prepare 8 sterile test tubes and number them 1-8. All tubes are filled with 1 ml of MHB media 2X concentration, then 1 ml of the sample to be tested is inserted into the first test tube then mixed so that a dilution of 1: 2 v / v occurs. 1 ml of the first test tube is transferred to the next test tube which already contains 1 ml of MHB media 2X concentration, the step is repeated until the 6th test tube (so that a dilution of 1: 2 is obtained, 1:4, 1:8, 1:16, 1:32, 1:64)¹⁶.

In the 6th test tube, discard 1 ml while in the 7th and 8th tubes, it is filled with 1 ml of NS then mixed and discarded 1 ml. In test tubes 1-7, it is filled with 100 µl of *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria suspension prepared in the previous step. The 8th test tube was not filled with bacterial suspension as a negative control. Then the next 8 test tubes were incubated at 37°C for 20-24 hours. In determining the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC), the last test tube is seen before turbidity or precipitation is seen. The test was carried out until it obtained the same MIC value three times¹⁶. The same was done with *Escherichia coli* bacteria.

Minimum Bactericidal Concentration Measurement

The MBC measurement was determined from the MIC test tube, which is 1 dose below KHM, KHM dose, and 2 – 4 doses above MIC. Next Petri *Nutrient Agar* (NA) dish were divided into 6 parts. Each test tube is selected, then inoculated as much as 50 µl on solid media (*Nutrient Agar*) and streaking on one part. The step was repeated three times. *Nutrient Agar* is incubated at a temperature of 37 ° C for

20 – 24 hours, then determines the MBC by looking at the last concentration before bacterial growth is seen¹⁶.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data on phytochemical test results of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract were analyzed descriptively¹⁷. Zone of Inhibition (ZOI) test data were tested for normality and homogeneity to determine normal distributed data ($p > 0.05$). After the data was normally distributed ($p > 0.05$) and homogeneous, then the *One Way Analysis of Variance* (ANOVA)⁴⁶ test was carried out. All statistical needs are carried out using *the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences* (SPSS) version 17. Data on the test results of MIC and MBC are described accompanied by supporting photos and presented in table form¹⁸

Results and Data Analysis

Phytochemical test results

Phytochemical testing was carried out qualitatively by identifying such compounds based on color changes in the sample. The phytochemical test results in table 1 show that *Aloe vera ethanol extract* contains flavonoids and alkaloids.

Table 1. Phytochemical test results of *Aloe Vera Ethanol Extract*

Testing	Result	Information
Flavonoids	+	Yellow
Phenolic	-	No color change
Saponins	-	No foam visible
Alkaloids	-	No white precipitate
	+	A brown precipitate was observed
Terpenoids	-	No color change

Description: (-): not detected, (+): detected

Bacterial Inhibition Test Results

Figure 1. Measurement of the inhibitory power of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Description: (1) 100% *Aloe vera* ethanol extract, (2) 50% *Aloe vera* ethanol extract, (3) 25% *Aloe vera* ethanol extract, (4) 12.5% *Aloe vera* ethanol extract, (5) 6.25% *Aloe vera* ethanol extract, (6) *Aloe vera* ethanol extract 3.125%, (Aq) aquades, (E70%) 70% ethanol, (A) amoxicillin, (T) tetracycline.

Table 2. Results of measuring the inhibitory power of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Replication	ZOI diameter (mm)									
	Aquades	Etha-nol 70%	100% <i>Aloe vera</i> Extract	<i>Aloe vera</i> Ex-tract 50%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Ex-tract 25%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Ex-tract 12.5%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Ex-tract 6.25%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Ex-tract 3.125%	Amoxicillin	Tetracycline
Mean ± SD	0 ^a	0 ^a	20.67±1.53 ^c	7.67±0.58 ^b	0 ^a	0 ^a	0 ^a	0 ^a	36 ^c	34 ^d

Description: Statistical analysis using the One Way ANOVA test then continued the Post Tukey test using a significant level of $p < 0.05$. Significant differences are shown by different letter notations, including: a) *Aloe vera* extract is 100% significantly different, b) *Aloe vera* extract is 50% significantly different, c) Amoxicillin antibiotics differ significantly, d) Tetracycline antibiotics differ significantly.

The results showed that *Aloe vera* extract had antibacterial effects against *Staphylococcus aureus* at a concentration of 50% and 100% (7.67 ± 0.58 mm and 20.67 ± 1.53 mm) $P < 0.05$. Both concentrations have lower potency than the control of amoxicillin (36 mm) and tetracycline (34 mm) $P < 0.05$. However, *Aloe vera* ethanol extract concentration of 100% had a very strong inhibitory power against *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria.

Figure 2. Results of measurement of the inhibitory power of *Escherichia coli*

Description: (1) 100% *Aloe vera* ethanol extract, (2) 50% *Aloe vera* ethanol extract, (3) 25% *Aloe vera* ethanol extract, (4) 12.5% *Aloe vera* ethanol extract, (5) 6.25% *Aloe vera* ethanol extract, (6) *Aloe vera* ethanol extract 3.125%, (Aq) aquades, (E70%) 70% ethanol, (A) amoxicillin, (T) tetracycline.

Table 3. Results of inhibitory power measurement of *Escherichia coli*

	ZOI diameter (mm)									
Replication	Aquades	Ethanol 70%	100% <i>Aloe vera</i> Extract	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 50%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 25%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 12.5%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 6.25%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 3.125%	Amoxicillin	Tetracycline
Mean ± SD	0 ^a	0 ^a	27.67±1.15 ^c	7.33±0.58 ^b	0 ^a	0 ^a	0 ^a	0 ^a	45 ^e	36 ^d

Description: Statistical analysis using the One Way ANOVA test then continued the Post Tukey test using a significant level of $p < 0.05$. Significant differences are shown by different letter notations, including: a) *Aloe vera* extract was 100% significantly different, b) *Aloe vera* extract was 50% significantly different, c) Amoxicillin antibiotics differ significantly, d) Tetracycline antibiotics differ significantly.

The results showed that *Aloe vera* extract had antibacterial effects against *Escherichia coli* bacteria at concentrations of 50% and 100% (7.33 ± 0.58 mm and 27.67 ± 1.15 mm) $P < 0.05$. Both concentrations had lower potency than the control of amoxicillin (45 mm) and tetracycline (36 mm) $P < 0.05$. However, *Aloe vera* ethanol extract concentration of 100% has a very strong inhibitory power against *Escherichia coli* bacteria.

Minimum Inhibition Concentration and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration

Figure 3. MIC test results of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Table 4. MIC test results of *Staphylococcus aureus*

MIC Test	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 100%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 50%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 25%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 12.5%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 6.25%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 3.125%	Bacterial control <i>S. aureus</i>	Control (-)
MIC Test	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-

Description: Table 4 shows the results of MIC testing on *Staphylococcus aureus*. A sign (+) indicates bacterial growth. While the sign (-) indicates no bacterial growth.

Table 4 shows the results of MIC testing of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract against *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria. The Minimum Inhibited Concentration (MIC) of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract occurs at a concentration of 12.5%. Bacterial growth can be seen from media that becomes cloudy or there are deposits. The higher the growth of bacteria in the media, the more turbid the media¹⁹.

Figure 4. MBC test results of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Description: The number of bacterial colonies grown on the streak plate is based on the concentration of *Aloe vera* extract.

Table 5. MBC test results of *Staphylococcus aureus*

MBC Test	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 100%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 50%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 25%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 12.5%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 6.25%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 3.125%
MBC Test	-	-	-	-	+	+

Description: Table 5 shows the results of MBC testing on *Staphylococcus aureus*. A sign (+) indicates that there is still bacterial growth on the scratch. While the sign (-) indicates no bacterial growth on the scratch results.

Table 5 shows the results of the MBC test of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract against *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria. The MBC of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract occurred at a concentration of 12.5%. The determination of the MBC value is seen from the absence of bacterial growth on the streak plate results which indicates that each test bacteria died due to the test solution at that concentration¹⁹.

Figure 5. MIC test results of *Escherichia coli*

Table 6. MIC test results of *Escherichia coli*

MIC Test	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 100%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 50%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 25%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 12.5%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 6.25%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 3.125%	Bacterial control <i>E.coli</i>	Control (-)
MIC Test	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-

Description: Table 6 shows the results of MIC testing on *Escherichia coli*. A sign (+) indicates bacterial growth. While the sign (-) indicates no bacterial growth.

Table 6 shows the results of MIC testing of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract against *Escherichia coli* bacteria. The MIC of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract occurs at a concentration of 25%. Bacterial growth can be seen from media that becomes cloudy or there are deposits. The more fertile the growth of bacteria in the media, the more turbid the media¹⁹.

Figure 7. MBC test results of *Escherichia coli*

Description Figure 7: The number of bacterial colonies grown on the streak plate is based on the concentration of *Aloe vera* extract.

Table 7. MBC Test Results of *Escherichia coli*

MBC Test	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 100%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 50%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 25%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 12.5%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 6.25%	<i>Aloe vera</i> Extract 3.125%
MBC Test	-	-	-	+	+	+

Description: Table 7 shows the results of MBC testing in *Escherichia coli*. A (+) sign indicates that there is still bacterial growth on the scratch. While the sign (-) indicates no bacterial growth on the scratch results.

Table 7 shows the results of the MBC test of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract against *Escherichia coli* bacteria. The MBC of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract occurs at a concentration of 25%. The determination of the MBC value is seen from the absence of bacterial growth on the streak plate results which indicates that each test bacteria died due to the test solution at that concentration¹⁹.

Discussion

Phytochemical Test Results

The results of phytochemical tests found that *Aloe vera* ethanol extract contains a class of active compounds flavonoids and alkaloids. Ethanol is a polar solvent and has properties that make it easy to attract secondary metabolites in optimal quantities. Polar compounds tend to be extracted with polar solvents whereas nonpolar compounds tend to be extracted with nonpolar solvents. Therefore, ethanol solutions that are polar are easier to extract polar compounds such as flavonoids and alkaloids^{20,21}.

Flavonoids are a class of phenol compounds that are polar, and generally will be dissolved by solvents with the same polarity properties as ethanol²⁰. The class of alkaloid compounds can dissolve in nonpolar solvents and most dissolve in polar solvents because alkaloids are a class of organic compounds containing nitrogenous bases that are alkaline²³. Therefore, extraction requires the addition of hydrochloric acid. The addition of hydrochloric acid aims to extract alkaloids that are alkaline using an acid solution²⁴.

Zone of Inhibition (ZOI) Test Results

Zone of Inhibition (ZOI) measurements on the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* bacteria at 50% concentrations of 7.67 mm and 7.33 mm while at 100% concentrations of 20.67 mm and 27.67 mm. *Aloe vera* ethanol extract with a concentration of 100% has a higher inhibitory power than other concentrations due to its higher antibacterial content. The amount of extract concentration given will affect the size of the inhibitory zone because it is influenced by the bioactive components contained in the extract²⁷. The higher the concentration of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract given, the greater the diameter of the inhibitory zone formed.

Aloe vera extract contains various classes of active compounds that have antibacterial activity. The class of active compounds is in the form of flavonoids and alkaloids. Flavonoids act as antibacterial by inhibiting nucleic acid synthesis and inhibiting cell membrane function. In inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis, the A and B rings of flavonoids play an important role in the process of interclassiation or hydrogen bonding, by accumulating nucleic acid bases so as to inhibit the formation of DNA and RNA²⁸. The mechanism of action of flavonoids in inhibiting cell membrane function by forming complex compounds from extracellular proteins so as to damage bacterial cell membranes and followed by the release of intracellular compounds²⁹. While alkaloids as antibacterial by disrupting the constituent components of peptidoglycan in bacterial cells, so that the bacterial cell wall layer is not formed intact and causes bacterial cell death³⁰.

Tetracycline and amoxicillin antibiotics have a broad antibacterial spectrum, effective against gram-positive as well as gram-negative bacteria^{31,32}. Tetracycline is bacteriostatic by inhibiting protein synthesis. This is done by blocking aminoacyl-tRNA bonds to the mRNA-ribosome complex. The tetracycline receptor is in subunit 30S³³. Tetracycline will bind to the ribosomal unit of the 30S bacterial cell so that the t-RNA does not attach to the ribosome resulting in the non-formation of aminoacetyl RNA³⁴, while amoxicillin works by binding to the penicillin bond protein 1A (PBP-1A) located in the bacterial cell wall³⁶. Thus, causing an inhibition at the final stage of peptidoglycan synthesis transpeptidase in the bacterial cell wall. This leads to inhibited cell wall biosynthesis and bacterial cell lysis where β -lactam compounds bind one or more penicillin-protein bonds³⁷.

Staphylococcus aureus and *Escherichia coli* bacteria are more effectively inhibited by tetracycline and amoxicillin compared to *Aloe vera* ethanol extract. This is because tetracycline and amoxicillin are pure antibiotics with a broad spectrum that can inhibit gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, while *Aloe vera* extract is a crude extract that has a mixture of various secondary metabolite compounds that affect the ability to inhibit bacteria³⁸.

Minimum Inhibition Concentration Test Results

The test results of the MIC of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract against *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria by 12.5% and against *Escherichia coli* bacteria by 25%. The MIC of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract was smaller against *Staphylococcus aureus* compared to against *Escherichia coli*. This could be because the cell wall arrangement of gram-positive bacteria is simpler, consisting of simple polysaccharides and contains teichoic acid, while gram-negative bacteria are more complex cell wall composition consisting of a number of proteins, lipids, polysaccharides, but no teichoic acid. This is why gram-positive bacteria are more sensitive to antibacterial compounds than gram-negative bacteria⁴⁰. Antibacterial compounds are compounds that can interfere with the growth or metabolism of bacteria. Based on the nature of toxicity,

antibacterial can inhibit bacterial growth (bacteriostatic) and kill bacteria (bactericidal). Bacteriostatic antibacterial only inhibits bacterial growth and is not lethal, while bactericidal can kill bacteria⁴¹.

Minimum Bactericidal Concentration Test Results

The test results of the MBC of *Aloe vera* ethanol extract against *Staphylococcus aureus* by 12.5% and against *Escherichia coli* by 25%. The higher the concentration used, the greater the antibacterial effect. This happens because more and more active compounds are contained in *Aloe vera* extract. The higher the concentration of *Aloe vera* extract, the more antibacterial active ingredients. The addition of the concentration of antibacterial compounds is thought to increase the penetration of antibacterial compounds into the inside of bacterial cells which will damage the cell metabolic system and can result in bacterial cell death³⁹.

Conclusion

Based on the results of phytochemical tests, it was found that *Aloe vera* ethanol extract contains flavonoids and alkaloids. Meanwhile, based on the results of statistical analysis, it can be concluded that *Aloe vera* ethanol extract concentration of 100% has a very strong inhibitory power against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* which was lower than tetracycline and amoxicillin antibiotics. Based on the results of the MIC and MBC tests showed that *Aloe vera* ethanol extract had MIC and MBC against *Staphylococcus aureus*, which was 12.5% and against *Escherichia coli* by 25%.

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